

Figure

Fig. 1 Geophysical observations of the continental mid-lithospheric discontinuity (MLD) modified after Fu et al., 2022[1], with data of plate motion from Liu et al., 2022[2] and azimuthal anisotropy at 260 km from Becker et al., 2016[3].

Fig. 2 Evolution of the model with $\Delta T = 300^{\circ}C$ and $\Delta = 15 \text{ kg}/m^3$. (a)-(c) Evolution of the material and velocity fields. Red arrows represent the direction and scale of the mantle flow velocity. (d)-(f) Details model evolution at the Craton margin, showing the development of a high strain-rate belt and a relative displacement between the upper and lower cratonic lithospheric mantle. (g) Evolution of the relative displacement for models with $\Delta = 15 \text{ kg}/m^3$ at different temperature settings.

Fig. 3 Model result types based on the density deviations ($\Delta\rho$) and temperature deviations (ΔT). (a) and (b) correspond to conditions without mantle flow and with mantle flow, respectively. Density and temperature data of various Cratons are also plotted.

Fig. 4 Deformation mechanisms of rocks in high strain rate belts and effects on S-wave velocity. (a) Distribution of random selected points in the high strain rate belt of model ($\Delta T = 300^\circ C$ and $\Delta \rho = 0 \text{ kg/m}^3$). (b)-(c) compare the high strain rate belt in the models ($\Delta \rho = 0$, $\Delta T = 0-400^\circ C$) with the deepest earthquakes in terms of temperature, pressure, and strain rate. (d)-(e) show the mantle peridotite was reworked to mylonitic peridotite under dry cratonic lithosphere mantle condition (modified after [4]). (f) shows the S-wave velocity reduction of the mylonite compared to host rock. (g) shows the S-wave velocity reduction of MLD in various cratons, where they were similar to rate of reduction shown in (f).

Fig. 5 Simplified conceptual model of MLD formation and growth, fluids-rich weak zone formation and delamination of the lower CLM along a fluid-rich weak zone. (a) MLD initially forms at the craton margin, generating a low permeability mylonite belt. (b) The MLD is constantly growing inland, hindering upward transport of fluids. (c) The accumulation of fluids forms fluid-rich weak zone. (d) As the fluid-rich zone weakens to a certain extent, delamination of the lower CLM occurs along this weakened zone under mantle flow, where the MLD is turned into a new LAB. UCLM, upper cratonic lithospheric mantle, LCLM, lower cratonic lithospheric mantle, MLD, mid-lithospheric discontinuity, LAB, lithosphere-asthenosphere boundary.

Fig. S1 The initial setup of the model, including material field, density data, temperature data and viscosity data of the red line in the material field.

Fig. S2 The comparison of model result ($\Delta T = 300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\Delta\rho = 15\text{ kg/m}^3$) with geophysics detected MLD in North American Craton. (a) The geometry of high strain rate belt shows flat pattern inside the CLM and curving upwards at the margin. (b) The MLD detected in North American Craton (modified by Yuan and Romanowicz, 2010)[5]. The model result shows the geometric similarity to the geophysical detected MLD in North American Craton.

Table

Parameter	Symbol	Units	Diffusion Creep		Dislocation Creep		
			Dry olivine ¹	Dry olivine ¹	Dry quartzite ²	Diabase ³	Wet quartzite ²
Stress exponent	n	-	1	3.5	2.4	3.05	2.3
Prefactor	B	$Pa^{-n} \cdot s^{-1}$	1.5×10^9	1.1×10^5	6.7×10^{-6}	3.2×10^{-20}	3.2×10^{-4}
Activation energy	E	$J \cdot mol^{-1}$	3.75×10^5	5.3×10^5	1.56×10^5	2.76×10^5	1.54×10^5
Activation volume	V	$m^3 \cdot mol^{-1}$	6×10^{-6}	11×10^{-6}	0	0	0

Table S1 Creep parameters used in this study. Numbers in brackets refer to the following reference: Dry olivine¹ [6]; Dry quartzite² [7]; Diabase³ [8].

Parameter	Symbol	Units	UCLM	LCLM	OCLM	AS	UC	LC	OC
Rheology			Dry olivine ¹	Dry olivine ¹	Dry olivine ¹	Dry olivine ¹	Dry quartzite ²	Dry quartzite ²	Diabase ³
Density	ρ_0	$kg \cdot m^{-3}$	3300	3285, 3300, 3315	3300	3300	2700	3000	3000
Shear modulus	G	Mpa	50	50	50	50	50	40	50
Cohesion	c	Mpa	20	20	20	20	30	30	20
Friction angle			30	30	30	30	10	10	10
Radioactive heat	H_r	$W \cdot m^{-3}$	0.1	0	0	0	1	0.4	0.4

Table S2 Model parameters used in this study. Numbers in brackets refer to the following reference: Dry olivine¹ [6]; Dry quartzite² [7]; Diabase³ [8]. Thermal expansivity $\alpha = 3 \times 10^{-5} 1/K$, compressibility $\beta = 1 \times 10^{-11} 1/Pa$, heat capacity $C_p = 1000 J/(kg \cdot K)$, thermal conductivity $k = 1.5 W/(m \cdot K)$ for UC, LC, OC and OCLM, $k = 1.0 W/(m \cdot K)$ for UCLM, LCLM and AS. UCLM = upper cratonic lithospheric mantle, LCLM = lower cratonic lithospheric mantle, OCLM = oceanic cratonic lithospheric mantle, AS = asthenosphere, UC = upper crust, LC = lower crust, OC = oceanic crust. ρ is temperature-pressure-dependent density and can be calculated as: $\rho = \rho_0 [(1 - \alpha(T - T_0))(1 + \beta(P - P_0))]$ at the reference temperature $T_0 = 298 K$ and reference pressure $P_0 = 10^5 Pa$.

Model number	ΔT ($^{\circ}C$)	$\Delta \rho$ (kg/m^3)	ΔF (mm/y)	Model results type
1	0	-15	20	Stable Type
2	0	0	20	Stable Type
3	0	15	20	Stable Type
4	100	-15	20	Stable Type
5	100	0	20	Stable Type
6	100	15	20	Stable Type
7	200	-15	20	Stable Type
8	200	0	20	Shear Type
9	200	15	20	Shear Type
10	300	-15	20	Shear Type
11	300	0	20	Shear Type
12	300	15	20	Shear Type
13	400	-15	20	Shear Type
14	400	0	20	Shear Type
15	400	15	20	Shear and Delamination Type

Table S3 The types of model results with different ΔT and $\Delta \rho$ at the condition of $\Delta F = 20 mm/y$, which has a similar distribution of results as $\Delta F = 10 mm/y$, indicating ΔF has a minor influence compared with ΔT and $\Delta \rho$ to the model results.

References

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